

THE CONCEPT OF SYMBOL IN THE STORY OF "A NEW ENGLAND NUN" BY M. FRIMEN.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10873144>

Abstract: Mary Wilkins Freeman's short story "A new England nun" delves into the complexities of symbolism, exploring how objects and settings can represent deeper thematic ideas within a narrative. This article will analyse and discuss the concept of symbolism in the story, highlighting the author's use of everyday objects to convey profound meanings.

Keywords: symbolism, short story, thematic implications, narrative technique, theme, character development

In "A New England Nun," Mary Wilkins Freeman skillfully employs symbolism to create a rich, layered narrative that explores themes of freedom, isolation, and personal choice. This article aims to explore the importance symbolism within the story and its contribution to the overarching themes and character development. By examining the use of everyday objects as symbols, we can gain insight into the deeper meanings and nuances embedded within Freeman's storytelling. The concept of symbol in "A New England Nun" is evident through the various objects and settings that Freeman utilizes to convey thematic significance. The use of symbols adds depth and richness to the narrative, inviting readers to engage with the story on a deeper level. One prominent symbol in the story is the canary bird, which represents Louisa's sense of duty and obligation. The canary is trapped in a cage, much like Louisa feels trapped in her narrow and isolated life. This symbol highlights the theme of confinement and the constraints placed upon Louisa by societal expectations and her own sense of duty. Another symbol is the little dog, Caesar, which represents Louisa's loyalty and steadfastness. Caesar has faithfully waited for her during her long engagement, mirroring Louisa's sense of duty and commitment to her fiancé, Joe. The dog also serves as a contrast to the canary, as it is free to roam the house and exhibits a sense of independence that

Louisa lacks. The white dress that Louisa carefully preserves and plans to wear on her wedding day is another symbol in the story. It embodies her ideals of purity, innocence, and the traditional role of a wife. The dress serves as a reminder of the life Louisa is expected to lead as married woman, and her reluctance to wear the dress reflects her ambivalence towards these expectations. Moreover, the locked bedroom symbolizes Louisa's hesitation and reluctance to move forward. It represents her fear of change and her inclination to remain in her safe, predictable world. The locked bedroom becomes a physical manifestation of Louisa's emotional and psychological confinement. Mary Wilkins Freeman's "A New England Nun" adeptly showcases the author's skill in utilizing symbolism to convey thematic depth and emotional resonance within her narrative. Through the use of everyday objects and settings as symbols, Freeman intricately weaves a story that explores the complexities of personal freedom, confinement, and individual agency. By dissecting the symbolic elements within the story, readers can gain a deeper appreciation for the nuances of Freeman's storytelling technique and the profound thematic implications embedded within "A New England Nun." We can say that M.Freeman was well-known not only for her skills to symbolize, but also for her best conveying capability. This short story is considered to be an exact example of her symbolitic writings.

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